

**DEVELOPING PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF THE FUTURE
ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHERS**

Jabbarov Ulugbek Abdurakhmanovich

Associate Professor, PhD at “Family and Gender” Scientific Research Institute, E-mail: jabborovulugbek1985@gmail.com

Safoyeva Rano Jalolovna

1st Year Doctoral Student of “Family and Gender” Scientific Research Institute, E-mail: rano_18@mail.ru

Abstract: At the current stage, the level of development of communicative professional competence in the system of higher pedagogical education has not been fully studied. The role and scope of professional communication in the higher education system and in the future professional activities of students, in self-determination and self-realization of their lives is not fully defined.

Key words: language teacher, competence, professionalism, level, lexicon, linguistics, communication.

Students' lack of understanding of moral knowledge and speech tools in their professional communication, lack of logical connection of their thoughts regarding their future professional specialty, inability to have a clear goal in their professional position, lack of skills to properly defend their point of view in confrontations, lack of ability to discuss professional tasks collegially, inability to distinguish cause from effect and inability to use professional terminology are observed. Also, graduates with high professional and scientific knowledge face difficulties and obstacles in professional relations because they do not know or do not follow the ethics of professional-social communication; cannot use professional terminology, cannot

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correctly and reliably defend their point of view, have difficulties in discussing and performing professional tasks.

The main reason for the existing shortcomings in the preparation of specialists for effective communication in a foreign language in the professional environment is the lack of unity in the development of professional and language experience in the process of teaching a foreign language in higher education institutions. These two experiences do not have a holistic view as a qualitatively new type of professional competence in the educational content.

This is due to the fact that most of the young teachers are poorly prepared when faced with real intercultural problems in a foreign language environment, bias in evaluations, lack of knowledge in the field of daily communication, insufficiently broad worldview, inability to adapt to new communication conditions, analysis or even inability to understand the existence of misunderstandings related to differences in cultures. we can see.

Currently, the formation of socio-cultural competence of students of higher education institutions in a foreign language is at a low level. As a result, students are not sufficiently prepared for their profession, along with the existence of a high enthusiasm and positive attitude towards communicating with representatives of the population of the country where the language is being studied. Future teachers do not fully master the lexicon of linguistics and country studies, which reflects the culture of the country where the language is studied, they do not know or have difficulty in applying socio-cultural models of verbal and non-verbal behavior, they are not familiar with everyday life and lifestyle in the countries where the language is being studied, they are overly concerned with the degree of similarity between national and foreign cultures. give high importance to the outside, their speech does not meet the requirements of authenticity, i.e. more attention is paid to linguistic factors, and they have less idea about extralinguistic factors that ensure the effectiveness of communication.

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Based on the obtained data, it can be concluded that a student of a higher educational institution of pedagogy does not meet the new requirements in terms of preparation in the direction of socio-cultural competence in a foreign language compared to a modern teacher. At the same time, it should be noted that there is a high interest of students in their future professional activities and a desire to communicate on professional topics. 46% of respondents were interested in everything related to their future profession, 24% have small ideas about their future profession, 23% are not satisfied with everything in it, but will not change to another one. And only 5% of students do not like their future profession, and 2% do not know anything about it.

Through questionnaires and surveys conducted with students, the following factors, which, in their opinion, are necessary for the teacher to improve the quality and effectiveness of vocational education in a foreign language were determined:

- more organization of live communication between teacher and students (16%);
- teacher's ability to interest students - (36%);
- giving more creative tasks - (7%);
- modeling communication situations using new methods (for example, group discussions based on competition) – (37%);
- creating a comfortable environment for communication (not interrogating students during classes, being friendly, being "closer" to students, understanding them, helping to overcome the psychological barrier in communication) - (18%);
- increasing the volume of educational materials, giving more assignments, increasing demand - (7%);
- clear description of the material - (6%);
- individual approach to students- (9%);
- discussion of professional topics in parallel with special topics - (10%).

The study of students' opinions showed that there is a high need to improve the quality of education and to increase the level of interest in mastering foreign professional communication among students.

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